

Studies on *bis*-N-Phenylhydroxamic Acids as Metal-Complexing Ligands: Part II. Adipyl *bis*-N-Phenylhydroxamic Acid

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Adipyl *bis*-N-phenylhydroxamic acid (RH₂) forms complex compounds with Cu(II), Fe(III), Al(III), V(V), and U(VI). The reagent has a tendency of forming tetradenate chelate rings. Compounds as CuR; Fe₂R₃·2H₂O; Al₂R(RH)₂(OH)₂·4H₂O and VO(OH)R are isolated. Molecules of water in iron and aluminium compounds are lost on heating for two hours at 120° and 108° respectively. Uranyl ion under different conditions forms two different compounds—the mono- and bis-compounds UO₂R·2H₂O and UO₂(RH)₂·5H₂O. These compounds become anhydrous by losing water molecules at 110° and 115° respectively.

In continuation of our work with succinyl *bis*-N-phenylhydroxamic acid¹, adipyl *bis*-N-phenylhydroxamic acid (RH₂) has been found to form compounds with Cu(II), Fe(III), Al(III), V(V) and U(VI). By lengthening the chain between the two hydroxamic acid residues in this reagent a tendency to act as a tetradentate ligand in the formation of chelates has been noticed.

The magnetic properties of some of these complex compounds have been studied. They appear to be high-spin complexes.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of Adipyl bis-N-phenylhydroxamic acid: It was prepared by the condensation of adipyl chloride (8 g.) with slight excess of recrystallized phenylhydroxylamine (10.5 g) in ice-cold ether solution containing 7.1 g of dry pyridine². The product was washed with ether and then thoroughly with water. The solid substance was extracted with a decinormal solution of ammonia and on acidifying the extract with dilute sulphuric acid (pH = 2) the compound precipitated. It was then recrystallized from hot rectified spirit and obtained as white shining crystals.

It is sparingly soluble in ether, insoluble in benzene, petroleum-ether but soluble in ethanol, m.p. 183° [Found: N, 8.6%, C₁₈H₂₀O₄N₂ requires N, 8.54%].

Preparation of Metal Chelates

1. *Copper (II) Compound*: To an excess of copper acetate in aqueous solution, solution of 1 g of reagent in ethanol was added with stirring. A green crystalline precipitate formed. pH was maintained at near about 4.5. The compound was filtered, washed with

1. Ghosh and Sarkar, *This Journal* 1968, **45**, 550.
2. W. O. Lukaschewitch, *Ann.*, 1936, **521**, 198.

sufficient water and finally with ethanol to remove any unreacted reactant. It was dried in air. This compound is insoluble in water and ethanol. It melted with decomposition at 211°. [Found $\mu_B = 1.87$ B.M.; Cu, 16.03; N, 7.26; CuR requires, Cu, 16.32; N, 7.19%].

2. *Iron (III) Compound* : To the ethanolic solution of 1.5 g of the reagent dilute ferric chloride solution was added (ratio Fe : RH₂ = 1 : 2) with thorough stirring. A red solution was obtained which on dilution with water formed an orange-red precipitate at pH ≈ 1.5 . The precipitate was filtered, washed with water and ethanol till free from reactants and dried in air. It is sparingly soluble in ethanol and insoluble in water. [Found : $\mu_B = 5.88$ B.M.; Fe, 9.75; N, 7.31%, Fe₂R₃, 2H₂O requires Fe, 9.90; N, 7.45%].

On dehydration at 120° to constant weight the loss corresponded to 2 molecules of water. [Loss found 3.16%; Calc. for 2H₂O 3.19%].

3. *Aluminium Compound* : An aqueous solution of 0.5 g of Al(NO₃)₃.9H₂O was mixed with an ethanolic solution of 0.6 g of the reagent with thorough stirring. When the pH was adjusted between 4.5 and 5.0 by adding aqueous sodium acetate solution a sponzy white precipitate appeared. It was washed with aqueous ethanol and recrystallized from rectified spirit. It is an water-insoluble white powder but readily soluble in ethanol. [Found : Al, 4.54; N, 7.41%, Al₂R(RH)₂(OH)₂.4H₂O requires Al, 4.74; N, 4.37%].

On dehydration at 108° the loss in weight corresponded to 4 molecules of water [Loss found 6.15%; Calc. for 4H₂O, 6.32%].

It may therefore be suggested that the original compound was probably Al₂R(RH)₂(OH)₂.4H₂O.

4. *Vanadium (V) Compound* : Ethanolic solution of the reagent was mixed with a slight excess of a solution of V₂O₅ in very dilute caustic potash, and the pH was adjusted to 2.5 by adding acetic acid. The mixture was warmed at 60° for 15 minutes when chocolate precipitate of the compound separated and was allowed to settle. It was filtered, washed with aqueous ethanol and finally recrystallized from ethanol and dried in air. It is diamagnetic. [Found : V, 12.51%; N, 6.72%; VO(OH)R requires V, 12.43% and N, 6.83%].

5. *Uranium (VI) Compound* : Two different compounds were isolated. (A) When a saturated aqueous ethanolic solution of 0.5 g. of reagent was added to an excess of UO₂-acetate (0.75 g) solution in aqueous ethanol with stirring a red coloured crystalline precipitate appeared. It was filtered, washed with aqueous ethanol (1 : 2) and recrystallized from hot rectified spirit and dried in air. [Found : U, 37.21; N, 4.61%; UO₂R.2H₂O requires U, 37.66; N, 4.43%].

On dehydration at 110° it lost 2 molecules of water and colour changes to deep brown. [Loss found 5.67%; Calc. for 2H₂O, 5.70%]. The anhydrous compound on keeping outside desiccator absorbs water and gradually regains its original red colour.

(B) A second compound formed on mixing with stirring an aqueous ethanolic (1 : 1) solution of uranyl acetate (0.40 g) with ethanolic solution of excess of the reagent (0.5 g). When the pH was carefully adjusted to about 2.5 the light brown precipitate appeared. It

was filtered, washed with aqueous ethanol and finally recrystallized from hot rectified spirit and dried in air, m.p. 161°. [Found : U, 23.56; N, 5.53; $\text{UO}_2(\text{RH})_2 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires U, 23.47; N, 5.53%].

On complete dehydration at 115° this light brown compound changed colour to deep brown. [Loss found : 8.82%, Calc. for $5\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 8.88%].

Nitrogen in these compounds was determined by modified Kjeldahl's method³.

Further work with such reagents is in progress in this laboratory.

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3. Ma *et al.*, *Microchim Acta*, 1957, 368.